

A STUDY OF SOCIO-ECONOMIC STATUS ON SELF CONFIDENCE OF THE ASPIRANTS FOR PREPARING OF COMPETITIVE EXAMINATION

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ABSTRACT:

Many researchers studied and found that different level of self confidence among aspirants. So that the present study aimed to examine the self confidence among aspirants for preparing competitive examination. The sample of the present study consisted of 300 (150 High Socio-Economic Status, and 150 Low Socio-Economic Status) aspirants from different locality of Ranchi, Jharkhand. This study was used stratified random sampling technique and samples were done by using self confidence inventory (Rekha Gupta 1971). Result showed that Socio-Economic status play significant role in the self confidence among high socio-economic status and low socio-economic status aspirants. Low socio-economic status experiences significantly high self confidence than the high socio-economic status aspirants.

KEYWORDS:

SELF –CONFIDENCE, ASPIRANTS, INSTITUTE, SELF, SOCIO-ECONOMIC.

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INTRODUCTION

Self-confidence is an attitude about your skills and abilities. It means you accept and trust yourself and have a sense of control in your life. You know your strengths and weakness well, and have a positive view of yourself. You set realistic expectations and goals, communicate assertively, and can handle criticism. On the other hand, low self-confidence might make you feel full of self-doubt, be passive or submissive, or have difficulty trusting others. You may feel inferior, unloved, or be sensitive to criticism. Feeling confident in yourself might depend on the situation. For instance, you can feel very confident in some areas, such as academics, but lack confidence in others, like relationships.

Having high or low self-confidence is rarely related to your actual abilities, and mostly based on your perceptions. Perceptions are the way you think about yourself and these thoughts can be flawed.

Low self-confidence might stem from different experiences, such as growing up in an unsupportive and critical environment, being separated from your friends or family for the first time, judging yourself too harshly, or being afraid of failure. People with low self-confidence often have errors in their thinking.

Confidence is the state of being clear-headed: either that a hypothesis or prediction is correct, or that a chosen course of action is the best or most effective. Confidence comes from the Latin word *fidere* which means "to trust".

In contrast, arrogance or hubris is a state of unmerited confidence belief lacking evidence and/or a reason. Overconfidence or presumptuousness is excessive belief in success without regard for potential failure. Confidence can be a self-fulfilling prophecy, as those without it may fail because they lack it, and those with it may succeed because they have it rather than because of an innate ability or skill.

Self-confidence is trust in oneself, one's personal judgment, ability, power, etc. one's self-confidence often increases as one satisfactorily completes particular activities. Self-confidence involves a positive belief that one can generally accomplish what one wishes to do in the future. Self-confidence is not the same as self-esteem, which is an evaluation of one's own worth. Self-confidence is more specifically trust in one's ability to achieve some goal, which one meta-analysis suggested is similar to generalization of self-efficacy. Abraham Maslow and many others have emphasized the need to distinguish between self-confidence as a generalized personality characteristic and self-confidence with respect to a specific task, ability, or challenge (i.e., self-efficacy). The term "self-confidence" typically refers to a general personality trait. In contrast, "self-efficacy" is defined by psychologist Albert Bandura as a "belief in one's ability to succeed in specific situations or accomplish a task" and refers to self-confidence that is expressed toward specific situations and objectives.

METHODOLOGY

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY:

- To proposed to assess the level of self confidence of the aspirants for preparing competetitive examination

HYPOTHESIS

There will be significant differences between high and low socio-economic status on self confidence of the aspirants for preparing of competitive examination.

SAMPLE

Sample size (300) 150 high socio-economic status and 150 low socio-economic status of the study: The present study aim to determined to assess the level of self confidence of the aspirants for preparing competetitive examination of the students healing from Ranchi District. The problem for the investigation has been a study of self confidence among aspirants for preparing competetitive examination.

Inclusion criteria: All participant are preparing competetitive examination, Participant ranged between the ages of 21 to 35 years, Educated up to BA and MA, Religion of Hindu, Muslim, and Christian, Gender Male and Female and all participant has been selected for only Ranchi District.

Exclusion criteria: Below 12th standard aspirants, below age range of 20 years and above 35 years, and out of Ranchi Jharkhand

TOOL USED

SELF CONFIDENCE INVENTORY

The Self Confidence Inventory (SCI) is designed (Rekha Gupta 1971) to assess self-confidence levels in adolescents and adults through a 56-item true-false questionnaire. The inventory has been standardized on a sample of 2074 individuals and demonstrates high reliability and validity, with coefficients ranging from .78 to .91. Scoring is based on responses, where lower scores indicate higher self-confidence, and norms for interpretation are provided.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

TABLE -1 MEAN SCORE OF HIGH AND LOW SOCIO-ECONOMIC STATUS ASPIRANTS OF COMPETITIVE EXAMINATION. ON SELF CONFIDENCE

GROUP	N	Mean	SD	t	df	significant
HIGH SES	150	68.63	4.73	2.08	298	.05
LOW SES	150	53.84	4.42			

Table 1. Shows that N, Mean and SD score of high socio-economic status aspirants were 150 & 68.63 and 4.73 respectively. while N, Mean and SD score of low socio-economic status aspirants were 150 & 53.84 and

4.42 respectively. The t value between two groups (high socio-economic status aspirants and low socio-economic status aspirants) was found 't'= 2.08. which shows there was significant difference between two groups. (df =298, p =0.05). The low socio-economic aspirants status having high self confidence and high socio-economic status aspirants having low self confidence

CONCLUSIN:

The study show that low socio-economic aspirants status having high self confidence and high socio-economic status aspirants having low self confidence the present study have been supported by the previous study by Edberg 2007.

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